

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal v1

Milestone 3.3

Work Package 3

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring
Milestone title	The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal v1
Milestone number	M3.3
Work package title	Data Standards, Data Linking, & Compatibility
Work package number	3
Lead beneficiary	UNESCO, EMBL-EBI
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Due date	30 April 2025
Initial submission date	30 April 2025 [v0]
First revision date	18 July 2025 [v1.0]
Second revision date	22 July 2025 [v1.1]
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Milestone

Executive Summary

The widespread adoption of NGS sequencing technologies has revolutionised aspects of biodiversity research and monitoring, by allowing analysis of environmental DNA (eDNA) in aquatic and other environments. This promoted an escalation of biological measurement capacity, wide taxonomic coverage and consistent data-driven findings. The data ecosystem covers a gamut of entities: sample collection, sequencing, sequence processing, taxonomic identification, based upon reference library construction and taxonomies. This ecosystem includes (meta)data repositories, (meta)data standards, schemas, and formats. The ecosystem also encompasses information that flows to and from the various agents and organisations involved. Furthermore it covers scientific papers and general scientific data repositories.

The current aquatic eDNA landscape has many unconnected or suboptimal links. Generally, the various data entities are stored in a plethora of repositories: regional, national, global and thematic, but also institutional and sometimes only within scientific papers. Different, and sometimes not acknowledged, standards are used in these repositories. As a result, the FAIR principles are not being fully applied, resulting often in data that is not easily found, is inaccessible or unusable. This applies to both research and commissioned biomonitoring of aquatic eDNA and impacts the European aquatic biodiversity scientific and governmental communities that are not being properly served.

Our mini-LLM exploration of scientific literature (Woollard et al. 2025) revealed the extent to which metadata about laboratory and bioinformatics workflows can be extracted from papers. This is however an expensive and unreliable way to extract metadata than simply pulling it in a machine readable state from the appropriate repository.

In this document, we outline the current state of the European, aquatic, eDNA data ecosystem. We then propose a future landscape in which the various gaps are addressed and the (meta)data flow made more FAIR, efficient, and sustainable. The proposed landscape outlined here, is currently in draft form, and will be finalised in the final deliverable from WP3. This future data ecosystem will be achieved by an increased adoption of interoperable standards, and an expansion of the minimal metadata being collected. A common theme is that of federation rather than centralisation, as this is a pragmatic response to the desire to have institutional, national, or thematic repositories, and to the cost of building new centralised repositories. Using agreed interoperable (meta)data standards and adopting widely-used web technologies (e.g. W3C) for data exposure and sharing, will increase the resilience of the overall data infrastructure, safeguarding against the case of any one resource ceasing to function, e.g. due to lack of resource or funding or other reasons. A proper data management plan created by each research group before embarking on the work, would make collection, collation and deposition of (meta)data to appropriate repositories more straightforward and efficient. Furthermore, engagement with standards organisations means that the standards will be more sustainable, have a wider community acceptance, and result in wider (meta)data interoperability. This will thus provide the European aquatic biodiversity scientific and governmental communities with more, and higher quality, data.

There will be significant financial costs associated with the improvements of the repositories, developing data management capacity within the community and also time costs associated with the researchers depositing more and better quality meta(data), but this will result in increased availability of valuable biodiversity data for decades and beyond. Furthermore, increasingly massive amounts of related data e.g. oceanographic data is being collected by remote sensing; simple metadata such as location (latitude, longitude) and date allows integration of valuable eDNA data alongside these physical/chemical information. It will contribute to getting continued value from the expansive research conducted across the European landscape and for the benefit of biodiversity life on earth.

The graphical current and future landscapes are what we recommend readers to concentrate on. This report includes a textual description that aims to provide further context and detail than could be provided on the map.

This draft proposal has benefitted from significant input from WP4 and WP5 to improve and finalise this current and future digital landscape.

Table of contents

Introduction.....	11
The graphical landscape proposal.....	12
The current landscape (higher resolution here).....	12
The future landscape (higher resolution here).....	12
Current landscape.....	13
Sampling Data.....	13
Laboratory Procedures.....	15
Raw Sequencing Data.....	16
Bioinformatics Analysis.....	18
Taxonomic Assignment.....	21
Processed Sequencing Data.....	23
Biodiversity data publishing of eDNA occurrences.....	26
Taxonomic backbones used in eDNA-based biodiversity (meta)data.....	28
Biobanks Data - Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility.....	30
Future landscape recommendations.....	35
Overall landscape.....	35
Sampling.....	38
Laboratory Procedures.....	38
Raw Sequence Data.....	38
Bioinformatics Analysis.....	39
Processed Sequence Data.....	39
Taxonomic assignment.....	39
eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases.....	41
Taxonomic backbone.....	43
Biobanks Data - Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility.....	43
Conclusion.....	45
Acknowledgements.....	45
Bibliography.....	46

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
BeBOP	Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices
BIN	Barcode Index Numbers
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BOLD	The Barcode of Life Data Systems
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DwC-A	Darwin Core Archive (a data standard)
DwC	Darwin Core (a metadata standard)
EC	European Commission
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EML	Ecological Metadata Language, a schema of XML
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
iBOL	International Barcode of Life
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data, a method of encoding linked data
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management Systems
LOD	Linked Open Data
MAG	Metagenome Assembled Genome
MDT	Metabarcoding Data Toolkit
MiXS	Minimum Information about any Sequence
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
OA	Open Access
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System

ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
PID	Persistent Identifier
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RDF	Resource Description Framework (a model for encoding semantic relationships between items of data)
SBDI	Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Suomen Ympäristökeskus
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards (previously Taxonomic Databases Working Group)
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology
UDE	Universitaet Duisburg-Essen
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WP	Work Package(s)
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Definitions

Table 1. Definition of some core terms as used here in the eDNA data ecosystem.

Term	Definition
Data	Scientific data created during research.
Dataset	Digital object(s) that include the results of the experiment/activity.
Sample	Material samples collected in the field.
Metadata	Metadata contained in or attached to datasets that provide relevant context, e.g. about the provenance, about the experimental setup, about bioinformatics, to provide discovery and description, etc.
Study Metadata	Describes the overall project, e.g. investigators, dates, places, related publications.
Sample Metadata	Describes where and how samples were collected, processed and stored.
Laboratory Metadata	Describes how samples were treated after collection and storage. E.g. DNA extraction, amplification, sequencing.

Bioinformatics Metadata	Describes the computational based aspects of the processing and analysis. Includes the software parameters, filtering etc..
Standard	A (meta)data “standard” means any type of agreed upon set of formats, schemas, vocabularies and methods for sharing/exposing data to ensure findability and accessibility. Ideally these are defined by an international standards body.
Occurrence	The existence of an organism (at a place and time).
Reference library	The reference (data) that was used to derive some result (for eDNA, taxonomic classifications) via a (programmatic) comparison.

Table 2. Descriptions of Resources relevant to the eDNA data ecosystem.

Resource	Description	URL
Algaebase	A database of information on algae, including terrestrial, marine, and freshwater organisms, providing taxonomic, distributional, and ecological data.	https://www.algaebase.org/
BODC	The British Oceanographic Data Centre provides a comprehensive range of marine data services, including data management, quality control, and dissemination of oceanographic and marine data.	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/
CHEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest is a freely available dictionary of molecular entities focused on 'small' chemical compounds, providing standardised information about their structures and biological roles.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/
DASSH	The Archive for Marine Species and Habitats Data serves as the UK's national repository for marine biodiversity data, ensuring long-term curation and accessibility of marine species and habitat information.	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/
DataONE	A distributed framework and sustainable cyberinfrastructure providing open, persistent, robust, and secure access to well-described and easily discovered Earth observational data.	https://www.dataone.org/
DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan is a biological database that collects DNA sequences, functioning as a member of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration alongside ENA and NCBI.	https://www.ddbj.nig.ac.jp/
DwC	Darwin Core is a standard designed to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing a stable framework for biodiversity data.	https://dwc.tdwg.org/
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network is a network of organizations supported by the EU's integrated maritime policy, providing access to marine data across various themes, including bathymetry, biology, chemistry, geology, human activities, physics, and seabed habitats.	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/

Resource	Description	URL
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive is a comprehensive database of nucleotide sequences from the European Bioinformatics Institute, offering open access to sequence data for the scientific community.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
ENVO	The Environment Ontology offers a controlled vocabulary for the environments in which biological entities live, supporting the consistent annotation of environmental data across various domains.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/envo
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biogeographic Information System is an online marine biogeographic database compiling data on all living marine creatures, aiming to centralise scattered biogeographic data collected by European institutions and make them freely accessible.	https://www.eurobis.org/
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments, providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.	https://www.gbif.org/
GEOBON	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network : A global network aiming to improve the acquisition, coordination, and delivery of biodiversity observations and related services to users.	https://geobon.org/
GEOSS	The Global Earth Observation System of Systems aims to connect existing Earth observation systems worldwide to promote collaboration and data sharing for informed decision-making.	https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php
GFBio	The German Federation for Biological Data offers a sustainable, service-oriented infrastructure for biological and environmental research data, supporting data archiving, management, and sharing.	https://www.gfbio.org/
GTDB	The Genome Taxonomy Database provides a standardised microbial genome taxonomy based on genome phylogeny, aiding in the consistent classification of bacterial and archaeal genomes.	https://gtdb.ecogenomic.org/
IBOL	The International Barcode of Life project aims to establish a globally accessible DNA barcode reference library, enhancing the ability to identify and discover species.	https://ibol.org/
IMOS	Integrated Marine Observing System is an Australian national collaborative research infrastructure delivering ocean observations to support marine and climate science.	https://imos.org.au/
INSDC	The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration archives nucleotide sequence data, from raw to assembled and annotated sequences, from around the world. Current members of INSDC are NCBI GenBank, DDBJ and ENA.	https://www.insdc.org/
INSPIRE	The Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the	https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/

Resource	Description	URL
	European Community aims to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure, facilitating the sharing of environmental spatial information among public sector organizations.	
ITIS	The Integrated Taxonomic Information System provides authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes, supporting consistent naming and classification across databases.	https://www.itis.gov/
MARBEF	Marine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning was a network of excellence integrating and disseminating knowledge on marine biodiversity, now serving as a legacy website with access to data and publications.	http://www.marbef.org/
MBON	Marine Biodiversity Observation Network is a global initiative to monitor and report on the status and trends of marine biodiversity to support conservation and sustainable use of ocean resources.	https://marinebon.org/
MGNify	A resource developed by EMBL-EBI that offers an automated pipeline for the analysis and archiving of microbiome data, aiding in the understanding of microbial communities.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/
MITOFISH	A comprehensive database of fish mitochondrial genomes, providing valuable information for studies in phylogenetics, population genetics, and species identification.	http://mitofish.aori.u-tokyo.ac.jp/
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information is a U.S. government agency that provides access to biomedical and genomic information, including the GenBank DNA sequence database.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System is a system under development by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO and is a global open-access data and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity for science, conservation, and sustainable development.	https://obis.org/
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System is a system under development by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, aiming to integrate existing ocean data and information systems into a collaborative, web-based network	https://odis.org/
OpenARIS	Open Access to Research Infrastructure in the South Caucasus and Central Asia aims to enhance the accessibility and visibility of research infrastructures in these regions.	https://www.openaris.com/
OTN	Ocean Tracking Network is a global research and technology platform tracking aquatic animals to understand their movements, habitats, and survival in the face of changing ocean environments.	https://oceantrackingnetwork.org/
PANGAEA	Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science is an	https://www.pangaea.de/

Resource	Description	URL
	open-access library for archiving, publishing, and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research, covering fields like oceanography, geology, and environmental sciences	
PlutoF	A cloud-based platform providing services for managing and publishing biodiversity data, supporting taxonomic, ecological, and genomic research.	https://plutof.ut.ee/
PR2	The Protist Ribosomal Reference database offers curated sequences of protist ribosomal RNA genes, supporting ecological and evolutionary studies of protists.	https://pr2-database.org/
QUOT	The QUOT project focuses on the quantification of ocean transport, aiming to improve the understanding of ocean circulation and its impact on climate.	https://www.quot.org/
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards is an international organisation that develops and promotes standards for the exchange of biological/biodiversity data to support the wider global community.	https://www.tdwg.org/
UNITE	A database providing molecular identification of fungi, offering a comprehensive resource for DNA-based identification and classification of fungal species.	https://unite.ut.ee/
World Data System and World Radiation Monitoring Centre	The World Data System supports universal and equitable access to quality-assured scientific data, while the World Ozone and Ultraviolet Radiation Data Centre archives global ozone and UV radiation data.	https://woudc.org/
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species is an authoritative and comprehensive list of names of marine organisms, aiming to provide the most accurate and up-to-date taxonomic information.	https://www.marinespecies.org/

Introduction

Climatic changes and human actions continue to affect Europe's aquatic environment and biodiversity. Sequencing technologies continue to evolve, with costs per sequenced base continuing to reduce and small sequencers that can be used in the field available, facilitating the collection and production of eDNA derived data for biodiversity monitoring. The computing and data infrastructures are also changing at pace. The mainstream adoption of FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and the advent of technologies such as semantic web, RDF, and Linked Open Data, provide increased community drive and potential solutions to particularly improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data. Increased data interoperability for machines, has benefits downstream in the ecosystem, including for AI.

The world of international science and politics offers many opportunities and challenges too, including limited government budgets, balancing national vs global priorities and a plethora of overlapping repositories. This all makes the value of our efforts to map the current eDNA landscape and proposing better pragmatic solutions even more important and urgent.

The eDNAqua-Plan project aims to landscape the current eDNA and reference library data landscape. Analysis from WP2 identified many gaps and highlighted two major use cases for aquatic eDNA measurements, (1) regular biomonitoring by governmental agencies and (2) academic research, that have different data flows. WP4 work produced different use cases of the data. WP3 ran a workshop (milestone 5 M3.1) in September 2024 focused on the standards of the current eDNA and reference library data ecosystem and naturally explored the related processes and stakeholders of the ecosystem. Task T3.3 has additionally researched how biobanks fit into this ecosystem and is currently mapping how different biodiversity repositories link to each other. A second WP3 workshop (milestone 6 M3.2), in January 2025, allowed us to brainstorm the current and future landscape. This milestone 7 M3.3 is a result of these joint efforts and describes the first version of digital ecosystem landscape proposals.

A cryptobenthic fish peeking through the reef. Credit: E. Boulanger

The graphical landscape proposal

The main output of the milestone 7 “First version of digital ecosystem landscape proposals prepared” is the generation of two landscape diagrams, representing both the current and the future aquatic eDNA data landscapes in a graphical form. These eDNA data landscape representations are shown below and can be downloaded in high resolution following the respective links.

The current landscape (high resolution pdf [here](#))

The future landscape (high resolution pdf [here](#))

To accompany these graphical representations, the text in the present document provides background information and further detail that we could not annotate onto the graphical landscapes.

Current landscape

Sampling Data

Sample metadata describes that which was collected from the environment. This information should provide the what (the material sample information), where (collection coordinates or region IDs), when (dates), how (instruments, protocols for sampling, storing, and processing), and who (agents and organisations). Sample metadata is arguably the most important metadata that is collected and provided, as the samples and their environmental context are the foundation of all subsequent data. This is particularly the case for eDNA and other biodiversity data. For any sequence data that is used, it is critical that the provenance of that data can be found.

Before data resulting from material samples are deposited, it is important to provide the overall study and sample metadata. For sequence data uploaded to an International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) database, this is typically captured in BioProjects (study level) metadata and BioSample metadata. The INSDC is currently composed of EMBL-EBI European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), the NCBI GenBank/SRA and the DNA Data Bank of Japan (DDBJ). The INSDC continuously share all their data and specifically give access to genetic and genomic sequence data that can be retrieved for metabarcode or metagenome identification.

BioSamples mainly uses MIxS vocabularies in its metadata. Some other sample resources use DwC. Fortunately there is some solid concept mapping already between MIxS and DwC.

Protocols that are followed, for sample collection and (pre-DNA extraction) processing, should be shared via protocol-specific publishers. This is a critical component of the provenance (Reusability) of the subsequent data.

Figure 1: For raw sequences that are deposited with INSDC(NCBI, ENA, DDBJ), the overall project/study is maintained in BioProjects, with the sample metadata e.g. sample collection information being maintained in BioSamples. Depending on the sample submission checklist chosen, most field names and the values are GSC MIxS compliant and map to DwC concepts. Some laboratory and bioinformatics workflow metadata is provided with the sample too, although not ideal.

For some eDNA studies, the taxonomy of the sample is known by virtue of the sampling site, or experimental design. The relevant sample metadata for such cases is described in the Taxonomy Data section. When the taxonomy of the sample is not known, the NCBI taxonomy offers a pseudo taxonomic identification that can be used: a Biome-level environmental taxonomy (e.g. “marine metagenome”).

What works well

- BioSample and BioProject provide an online way for the metadata for a project, study, and sample to be found and accessed: any subsequent dataset metadata record can refer to the BioSample PID to provide a link to the provenance of the data. BioSample and BioProject PIDs can be created for other data types as well, not only for DNA data.
- The nesting structure provided by BioProjects and Biosamples, for studies and samples, allows for projects which produce many different “strands” of related data to be accommodated.
- For many eDNA aquatic experiments the sample collection is particularly important. Where the metadata includes latitude and longitude, collection data and time, and even depth - there is much information that can be computationally derived from it.
- Protocol-specific publishers, e.g. protocols.io and OBPS, are a fantastic way to ensure that protocol documents are open access.

What does not work well

- Sample metadata is not always, or not fully, provided.
- Sequences deposited in the DNA-specific repositories of INSDC (NCBI, ENA and DDBJ) will typically be associated with BioSample and BioProject records.
 - However sequences that are published in generalist repositories, or are not published at all, will not usually be linked to BioSample and BioProject records.
 - Furthermore, the quantity and quality of the metadata fields is often suboptimal, even when metadata is in an INSDC database, as users do not always provide it or conform to a standard (Hassenrück et al. 2021). Thus interoperability is difficult.
- In particular, sampling and processing protocols are not often published in protocol-specific open repositories. Often, the field provided for collecting protocol information in the metadata requires only a protocol title or name - better would be to require the URI/DOI to an open access publication. In practice, sample, study and laboratory metadata are often not recorded in public repositories, with only the IDs of the deposited raw sequences linked to this information in scientific publications.
- One third of repositories analysed in the WP2 survey (Woollard et al. 2025) are missing any general sample or sequence related metadata e.g. GPS coordinate or library_strategy
- Some repositories are using global metadata standards, but many are not. DwC (e.g. OBIS and GBIF) and GSC MIxS (e.g. INSDC) are the most common where there are global standards. Indeed there is a MIxS TDWG DwC mapping task force, with the objective of improving interoperability between these two major standards. Where eDNA data is buried in papers or in Dryad etc., it is less likely to be using global standards.
- Difficult to query for aquatic environmental samples/raw sequence records from the INSDC archives. There are multiple parameters needed to get aquatic environmental samples from the INSDC archives in terms of coverage and accuracy.
- Barcode gene identification is inconsistent in INSDC. In the INSDC, barcode gene nomenclature for eDNA aquatic samples are rarely captured in the “target_gene” field and we

determined that only 20% recorded in the study description or title. The INSDC have no mandated Barcode marker identifiers.

- INSDC users sometimes use generic and not aquatic specific checklists. Generic sample checklists with less mandatory information are available at INSDC databases. Users sometimes tend to use these checklists instead of the more specific and metadata rich checklists, which limits data searchability and reusability.
- In practice, currently, sample, study and laboratory metadata are frequently not recorded or are recorded with minimal information, in raw sequence repositories. In most cases, the IDs of the raw sequences are linked to this information in scientific publications.
- Finding the correct term in standardised checklists for geographical locations (GAZ), habitats (ENVO) or laboratory machinery (OBI) is not straightforward as a specific vocabulary is needed to find the correct term. Difficulties in finding appropriate terms for the specific use cases pose hurdles for the operationalisation of the landscape.

Laboratory Procedures

Laboratory procedures include the process of extracting DNA from a sample, preparing sequence libraries, sequencing on an instrument and the initial bioinformatics to generate raw sequences.

The laboratory work starts with material samples and ends with data (raw sequences). The laboratory metadata that should be provided with these data need to include a link to the sample metadata, and information about the (subsequent) laboratory processing: and the what, where, when of the laboratory work, as well as who and how (e.g. the software and settings/parameters used).

The laboratory protocols that are followed should also be shared via protocol-specific publishers. This is a critical component of the provenance (Reusability) of the subsequent data.

Figure 2: Laboratory procedures are currently rarely (<10%) deposited in specialist public archives, such as protocols.io and now workflowhub (Woollard et al. 2025, Egge et al. 2025). Some information is in general archives of scientific papers. A limited amount of the laboratory related metadata is frequently captured in INSDC e.g. sequencing instrument is mandatory.

What works well

- The necessary metadata to describe the laboratory procedures can be provided via BioSamples and the experiment object when submitted to INSDC, in particular by providing these as protocol documents with a DOI/URL which can be added to the relevant metadata field.
- Sequencing specific metadata like the instrument or library preparation is in the experiment object in INSDC.
- Suitable repositories for laboratory protocols, such as the well established **protocols.io** exist.
- Using LLM the DNA extraction method and even protocol DOIs are possible to capture from the scientific paper (Woollard et al. 2025). Obviously it would be ideal if such advanced techniques are not needed.
- BioMonitoring by or on behalf of governments is more standardised in terms of what metadata and data is collected (Egge et al. 2025), although there are a variety of standards.
- Some laboratories, typically in large facilities, have LIMS that can automate metadata generation.

What does not work well

- Laboratory procedures should be fully described, as they constitute the provenance of any resulting data. This can be provided as separate, open access, linked, protocol documentation or as methodologies written directly into the metadata of the data. Unfortunately, enforcement of the second and provision of sufficient metadata fields for the first is lacking in the metadata of the various data repositories involved in this part of the ecosystem. Data producers – with the possible exception of those working within (EU-funded) projects – do not generally have a habit of publishing protocols in protocol-specific repositories, they often do it in scientific papers or even only as offline documents, and this needs to change. Currently no European or international standards outlining laboratory procedures exist, but work to develop such standards that in the future will formulate the minimum requirements of laboratory procedures as well as related metadata are underway in both ISO and CEN working groups.
 - From WP2 (Egge et al. 2025), a) the questionnaire analysis (60 responses), showed that for sequencing data only 51% reported DNA extraction methods, 56% the sequencing instrument or platform and only 2% the PCR protocol. b) BioSamples (INSDC) eDNA workflow (nucl_acid_ext, DNA_extraction_method or nucleic.acid.extraction) analysis showed that only between 1 and 6% submitted samples had relevant information.
 - This is consistent with a review of INSDC metadata (Hassenrück et al. 2021).
- The description of laboratory procedures in a machine-understandable way is even more uncommon. As machine-readability and understandability become more important, this is something that needs to be considered. Initiatives such as [BeBOP](#)¹ to provide machine-readable protocol templates are useful here.

Raw Sequencing Data

Raw sequences are DNA base pairs from the sequencing instrument with marginal processing, often just demultiplexing (if relevant to the sequencing strategy). Typically it is a FASTQ file, containing thousands of reads. This sequence file has minimal level of metadata (sometimes just an identifier), it will therefore need to be supplemented with the metadata from the sample and the laboratory procedures (experiment metadata), as described in the [Laboratory Procedures section](#).

¹ See also <https://www.protocols.io/view/bebop-protocol-templates-c2h3yb8n.html>

Figure 3. Raw sequencing data are generally deposited in INSDC databases (ENA, NCBI, DDBJ) where data are continuously exchanged and must follow minimal metadata requirements. In a few cases, data are deposited to generalist repositories such as Zenodo or Dryad, or kept offline, which are not easily findable or accessible.

What works well

- FASTQ sequence files are highly standardised in terms of format.
- INSDC repositories are set up to receive and archive such sequence files. These are associated with the sample metadata.
- The generation of proprietary file formats by sequencing instrument manufacturers is becoming less common, and INSDC accepts only standardised formats.

What does not work well

- eDNA raw sequence data is scattered through many repositories. Much eDNA raw sequence data is external to INSDC archives, which makes it difficult to find or reuse data. We were not able to determine exactly how much, but reviews (Jurburg et al. 2020, Leigh et al. 2024) have estimated up to 50% and this is supported by our LLM investigation analysing 1,438 biodiversity papers estimating 77% (Deliverable 2.2).
- The INSDC raw sequence only gets the taxonomy id initially provided on submission of the BioSample.. There is thus no update of the taxonomy in the raw sequence record as determined by downstream analysis.
- BioMonitoring data typically goes into agency or governmental repositories rather than public ones and non-disclosure agreements imposed by commissioners may also prevent data sharing (Egge et al. 2025).

Bioinformatics Analysis

Raw sequences need to be heavily processed before further analysis can be performed. The details of the processing vary depending on the sequencing technology used, e.g. single molecule sequencing (PacBio, ONT etc.) is rather different to multi-read next generation sequencing (e.g. Illumina/Solexa, MGI). Bioinformatics analysis can be performed with both general purpose ready-to-use and highly automated tools or customizable pipelines. Whatever is used, there can be much diversity of algorithms, parameters and versions. Bioinformatic processing pipelines typical for metabarcoding consist of the following steps: pre-processing and filtering of raw reads, merging of paired end reads, denoising, filtering out of artifacts and then clustering, with many different programs and underlying algorithms. The processed data obtained typically consists of a set of Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) (if a denoising method is followed) or Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) (if a clustering method is followed). The resulting tables typically consist of a list of ASVs or OTUs detected per sample and their read abundance in each sample. These ASVs or OTUs can then be taxonomically identified by comparing the obtained sequences to those in reference databases, yielding taxonomy tables (see also [Taxonomic Assignment](#) below). Many different softwares and algorithms exist to assign taxonomic information to sequence reads. The choices of data filtering method, denoising or clustering algorithm, reference database, assignment algorithm and parameter choices within the chosen algorithms or softwares greatly influence the resulting biodiversity assessment (as highlighted in the recent publication by Bayer et al. (2025) and the ongoing work of the [MARCO-BOLO Data Analysis Challenge](#)).

Any bioinformatics pipeline should thus be accompanied with descriptive metadata that include various details about the pipeline: the agents (author, maintainer, contact), licence, dates/version, URIs for download/access, software types, included algorithms and reference libraries, etc (e.g. a [CodeMeta](#) file). Any *outputs* of the bioinformatics processing should also be accommodated with provenance metadata: what pipeline was used (e.g. by referencing the URI of the CodeMeta file), what input parameters were used, who did the processing and when, and which sequences (given as PIDs, ideally as URIs) the processing was done on.

Figure 4: The steps, software and parameters for the bioinformatics processing of the raw sequencing data for metabarcoding can be archived as procedures in different repositories. These are captured as pipeline and workflow scripts in their original format, as well as fields in a metadata table.

What works well

- Many core sequencing and other major facilities have made use of workflow management systems.
 - These systematically record the bioinformatics processing workflows, the component programs, program parameter choices, and which output is input for which component.
 - Often these were based on Snakemake and Common Workflow Language (CWL). Over the last decade Nextflow has become more used.
 - Where these workflows are archived, they would thus provide useful information, however it is uncertain how machine interpretable they are all in data use context.
- Good repositories for bioinformatics workflows are emerging: Biocompute Object and Elixir WorkflowHubs.
 - protocols.io can be used for bioinformatics workflows, but is general.
 - GitHub is great for holding code and different versions of code, e.g. workflows.

- Examples of provenance tracking within bioinformatic workflows exist within the QIIME2 environment (<https://develop.qiime2.org/en/latest/framework/explanations/provenance.html>), that could be used as a blueprint for other systems as well.
- LLM analysis of scientific papers is sometimes able to determine the bioinformatics analysis workflow (Woollard et al 2025), but it would be better if this metadata was already systematically collected.

What does not work well

- Bioinformatics analysis outputs, especially when originating from custom scripts, are not often accommodated by metadata that describe those outputs in a way that make them reusable even to humans, let alone to machines (e.g. describing what the columns in the OTU table mean, including IDs that are also unique and accessible). While these details may well be described in scientific papers (which may or may not be open access) or accompanying “readme” (which may or may not be complete and understandable to all and is certainly not standardised), this is insufficient to provide the long-term reusability of the outputs.
- It is still the case that pipelines and scripts are often not completely provided via suitable, accessible, repositories but are provided only “upon demand” (which is effectively non-sustainable as bioinformaticians move to new jobs or forget where those pipelines and scripts are to be provided on demand).
- Documentation of bioinformatics analysis often lacks information on the computational environment that has been used. As a consequence, analyses may not be replicated because of incompatibilities with newer software. More complex bioinformatics analysis workflows should more often be containerised to assure reproducibility.
- Not all of the outputs of bioinformatics analysis are published.
 - While the data containing the interesting scientific outputs (e.g. the FASTA files, and later the OTU/ASV tables) are provided, the other outputs (e.g. intermediate files, QC results, etc) are often not.
 - There are a number of practical reasons for this, including a lack of natural homes to publish such data, and the quantity and volume of these data combined with the question of which particular parts of it to publish.
 - There is a tendency to assume that anyone wanting to know more will reprocess the data themselves; this ignores the facts that (1) not everyone has the resources or skills to do that, and (2) providing (some of) these intermediate files provides trustability in the results of the processing.
 - Community agreement on what to publish, and on how to provide that trustability without needing to publish everything, as well as templates to do this, is necessary here.
- Sometimes a comprehensive dump of the whole project, including results data and workflow (bioinformatics and laboratory) is deposited in Zenodo, Dryad or even FigShare. Whilst these are publicly accessible and archived, it will be difficult for machines to be able to find, interoperate and reuse this valuable information.

Taxonomic Assignment

Reference libraries

Sequences, ASVs, or OTUs obtained through the eDNA metabarcoding workflow can be taxonomically identified by comparing the obtained sequences to those in reference databases (libraries of known - i.e. with species names - sequences for specific barcodes or entire genomes). The current landscape of reference libraries used for metabarcoding can be subdivided in three different – hierarchical – database types, from the broad/primary nucleotide databases where data is generally published and harvested, down to quality-controlled and taxonomically curated reference libraries typically specialised in one or more taxonomic groups.

Nucleotide Databases

Nucleotide databases are broad-range databases hosting all types of sequence/molecular data ranging from mitochondrial and nuclear genomes to gene sequences, protein sequences and short barcodes. The EMBL-EBI European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) and the NCBI GenBank specifically give access to genetic and genomic sequence data that can be retrieved for metabarcode or metagenome identification. Together with the DNA DataBase of Japan (DDBJ) they continuously share all their data through the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC).

Quality-Control Databases

The middle layer consists of databases where data undergo quality control by checking the availability of metadata, albeit minimal. The nucleotide sequences are either harvested from the primary nucleotide databases above, or newly published. An important one here is the BOLD database. The BOLD database both harvests data from NCBI, and allows publishing new nucleotide sequences through their portal to NCBI. There is, however, no curation on the taxonomic assignment of the sequences submitted to BOLD.

Taxonomically Curated Databases

The inner/lowest layer consists of specialised libraries typically focusing on certain taxonomic groups and that have conducted taxonomic curation of their sequence data. Taxonomic curation consists of checking that genetically neighbouring sequences share homogeneous taxonomic names (by using phylogenetic tools, by checking taxonomic synonyms or by checking recent publications). This taxonomic curation is typically not reported back to the primary databases where sequence data was harvested from, with the exception of the feedback loop of annotations from the UNITE community to ENA through the Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH)².

For genomic data, various metadata portals exist including Genomes on a Tree (GoaT, <https://goat.genomehubs.org>) and the JGI Data Portal (<https://data.jgi.doe.gov/>) which allow to query species and point towards the available data locations.

² <https://unite.ut.ee/curation.php>

Figure 5. Overview of some of the (main) reference databases and their classification within the three reference database types.

The WP2 landscape analysis of reference databases highlights gaps and opportunities in the existing landscape (report D2.2). Their highlights are repeated here.

What works well

- Nucleotide sequence databases are well in place. They have the capacity to accept barcode & genome sequencing data (on top of others).
 - FASTA and FASTQ are the most common format for uploading and downloading DNA sequences, and TEXT or CSV formats are frequently used for metadata
- There are already good practices to submit all genetic data (barcodes & genomes) to these. Publishers already obligate the submission of sequence data, and most (big) projects have a pipeline to submit data to INSDC (e.g. BGE).
- Most quality-controlled and curated reference databases are active with ongoing uploads, though few update annually. GreenGenes2 leads with 20 million records, followed by SILVA with 15 million. Some databases are specialised, with FWAAlgaeDB for freshwater and others like NISdb and DUFA for marine records, while many do not specify environmental sources. Most reference databases store data on multiple DNA barcodes or molecular markers. This creates a wide diversity of resources available.
- From the WP2 questionnaire survey, most of the reported cases indicated to have deposited at least some DNA reference sequences in databases, around 82%
 - From those that were inferred to have deposited generated DNA reference sequences, 75% of the cases further informed that such were deposited in public databases. Every non-deposited report further stated that sequences will be deposited in public databases, with an exception in which no information was provided.
 - BOLD and NCBI were the most frequently used databases (both ca. 41% each).

- From the WP2 questionnaire survey, around 91% of the assessed cases reported to deposit metadata along with DNA reference sequences generated. Those that have not yet deposited stated that such is indeed expected.
 - The most commonly generated metadata included project identification, GPS coordinates, person collecting and identifying and depth/altitude.
 - However, metadata standards were not commonly followed, with more than half (ca. 55%) of those that deposited metadata along with DNA reference sequences reporting as so.
 - Specimens' images were only reported in about half of the replies.
- From the WP2 questionnaire survey, most of the reported cases, around 85%, indicated to be following a procedure for accepting or rejecting sequences, while four cases did not provide any information. Several approaches were reported, but sequence length and sequence quality analysis were found to be strongly the most employed according to the survey data
 - The employment of taxonomic curation procedures in the management of DNA reference sequences showed lower coverage, with approximately 64% of the cases reporting it. Three cases did not provide information.
- Most databases (81%) have a standardised structure, but MIDORI, OTT, µgreen, and MZGdb lack web interfaces. About 71% do not offer API support, and 62% lack desktop or console support. PR2, OTT, MDD, and Phytool provide all access types, while GreenGenes2 and MIDORI offer single-access methods. BOLD Systems and UNITE support web interfaces with APIs, and SILVA, GTDB, and FWAAlgaeDB offer both web and desktop access.

What does not work well

- In-house databases are not FAIR. They are often developed aside from eDNA studies and do not follow the same obligations to publish sequence data to INSDC.
- Sequence data is published but essential metadata is missing to allow proper reuse. From the WP2 assessment of DNA barcode reference libraries, mandatory metadata was only available from BOLD Systems and MDD, including taxonomic assignments and sample locations. While GPS coordinates were present in about a third of databases (e.g., BOLD Systems, SILVA, UNITE), most databases lacked detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequence protocols. Only NISdb, DUFA, and MDD provided comprehensive workflow details.
- Even then, the check on the availability of metadata in quality-control databases is mostly very minimal. There are very often not even geographic coordinates.
- Some level of taxonomic curation is used by about 86% of DNA reference databases, except Metabarpark, OTT, and GreenGenes2. Most databases (76%) however lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications, with only a few— EukRibo, BOLD Systems, UNITE, MDD, and GreenGenes2—offering this feature. GSR lacks taxonomic identification features but includes taxon names.

Processed Sequencing Data

Processed sequencing data comprises the data after it has gone through the bioinformatic treatment steps, including (non exhaustively) quality filtering, merging of paired-end reads, denoising or clustering and taxonomic assignment. The final format comprises either a table of ASV or OTUs and their read abundances in each sample, and assigned taxonomies for each ASV or OTU if the sequences could be taxonomically identified. Only very little processed sequencing data are currently being deposited in findable and interoperable databases.

The ASV/OTU tables are currently being deposited either in supplementary materials of scientific papers or in generalist data repositories such as Dryad, Figshare or Zenodo. A few projects have their own databases e.g. Tara Ocean's Ocean Read Atlas <https://ora.mio.osupytheas.fr/> and associated databases, the Swedish ASV portal <https://asv-portal.biodiversitydata.se/> (Prager et al. 2023) or the German Barcode of Life (GBOL) ASV registry <https://data.bolgermany.de/gbol1/metabarcoding> (Braunig et al. 2024). No general repository for depositing ASV/OTU data in standardised format is currently in common use. Biodiversity data publishers such as OBIS, GBIF and their respective nodes accept DNA-based occurrence data following the DwC-A format and standard, practically making them ASV/OTU repositories. While this is relatively new, the community around this is active, and the standard as well as access to this data is under continuous review and improvement. The Targeted Locus Study object submitted to NCBI (NCBI TLS) could be a place to deposit ASV/OTU data. ENA is currently developing analysis objects for submission of ASV/OTU tables and its taxonomic identification (linked to NCBI taxonomy identifiers).

After taxonomic assignment, the ASV and OTU data containing taxonomic IDs and constituting taxonomy tables are mostly being deposited either in supplementary materials of scientific papers or in generalist data repositories such as Dryad, Figshare or Zenodo. The number of taxonomically assigned eDNA datasets deposited in the biodiversity data publishers OBIS and GBIF is growing, although taxonomic assignment is not strictly necessary as sequences can also be recorded as unknown. Depositing processed eDNA data to biodiversity databases is however not common practice yet (see [Biodiversity data publishing of eDNA occurrences](#) below).

Processed sequencing data published to biodiversity databases should be accompanied with extensive metadata to allow for trust and reuse of the data. This metadata should cover and integrate essential information from the different major steps leading to the processed sequencing data: sampling, laboratory procedures, bioinformatic processing and taxonomic assignment, including information on manual curation.

With respect to the metadata to be provided with the pipelines and their outputs: the same comments apply as described in the Bioinformatics Analysis section. Any pipeline should be accommodated with metadata that describes *that pipeline*, and any outputs of the processing should also be accommodated with metadata that describes the *processing* that led to those data, as well as a link to the sequences on which the processing was done (and more specifically, also to the metadata of those sequences).

Data Flows

- A regular query from GBIF of ENA's SWAGGER API extracts the metadata of the biodiversity related sequence data in ENA for processing and ingestion into GBIF.
- MGnify queries raw microbiome sequences from ENA, then through bioinformatics analysis determines the taxonomic diversity and functional & metabolic potential of environmental samples. The resulting occurrence data is published to GBIF as well as OBIS.

Figure 6: Biodiversity occurrence eDNA related (meta)data is currently deposited in a plethora of generalist and specialist repositories. This can be in many different formats or no-structure. N.B. This is an extended graph of the below

What works well

- Many national biodiversity databases link their data to the global repositories OBIS and GBIF centralising access to them and making their data discoverable
- These all follow the same Darwin Core standard, with the DNA-derived data extension
- The [GBIF Metabarcoding Data Toolkit](#), which is also deployed for OBIS, makes formatting single or small datasets into DwC easy and lowers the hurdle to publish this type of data to biodiversity occurrence databases.
- For larger volume projects generating many datasets, different pipeline steps exist or are being developed to export data files into DwC-A.
 - The PacMAN pipeline developed by OBIS includes a DwC conversion step <https://github.com/iobis/PacMAN-pipeline>, although results are also available as OTU tables (phyloseq format)
 - The GEANS pipeline https://github.com/pascalhabluetzel/GEANS_WP4_dwca
 - The ANERIS project (<https://www.aneris.eu/>) develops a tool called MARGENODAT <https://aneris.eu/technology/MARGENODAT> to link bioinformatic workflows with biodiversity data repositories
 - The NOAA AOML 'Omics program is developing code to convert eDNA metabarcoding data to Darwin Core for OBIS <https://github.com/aomlomics/edna2obis>
 - The MGnify tool <https://github.com/gbif/mgnify-to-dwc> to extract MGnify studies to DwC archives
 - The ARMS-MBON DwC generator <https://github.com/arms-mbon/darwin-core-generator>

What does not work well

- Only a fraction of papers publishing eDNA studies share their processed data
- Of these, most are submitted in broad-scale repositories or in the scientific article's supplementary material. The problem with these is that they can only be accessed through the doi link given in the original paper. It is thus not easily Findable, often not Accessible.
- In addition, these broad-scale repositories (Dryad, Zenodo, Figshare, ...) do not enforce (meta)data standards. Datasets are thus submitted in variable formats, with variable (or insufficient) metadata making them not Interoperable or Reusable
- Repositories that do enforce minimal mandatory metadata still do not enforce the interoperability of the metadata provided (e.g. strings rather than URIs for vocabs and protocols). Many repos have data standards or data templates that need to be followed, but (1) do not always check the content to check the templates are conformed, (2) do not enforce interoperability of the content of the data. Requiring DwC is good because the metadata and data follow a standard that is interoperable, but it still has gaps due to insufficient mandatory fields and insufficient machine-interoperability.
- The ASV portal and ASV registry allow for sequence searches. It is unclear however whether the data published here is discoverable through biodiversity data publishers, hindering their findability and reusability.
- BioMonitoring data typically goes into agency or governmental repositories rather than public ones and non-disclosure agreements imposed by commissioners may also prevent data sharing (Egge et al. 2025).

Biodiversity data publishing of eDNA occurrences

After taxonomic classification, the resulting “occurrences” can be published in biodiversity repositories. There are many such repositories that now accept eDNA-based occurrences, between them covering the national, regional, thematic, and global scales. Task 3.3 has been looking at these particular stakeholders in the eDNA data ecosystem of Europe.

The largest global players in this part of the ecosystem are [GBIF](#) and [OBIS](#), which are fed by their various nodes and data providers. [EurOBIS](#), the European node of OBIS, and its partner [EMODNet](#), are also important in the European data space. The data standard used is DwC-A, with the [DNA-extension](#) to DwC-A being used to accommodate DNA-specific information. The metadata standard – the vocabulary used in the CSV files that make up the DwC dataset – is DwC, and this links to the MIxS standard for the omics-specific terms. This extension is currently not a standard as defined and maintained by [TDWG](#), but it is the standard used by GBIF, OBIS and EurOBIS. It is still undergoing some modifications as it is tested out on more and more DNA-based occurrence data.

There are numerous other biodiversity data publishers, some of which feed into OBIS and GBIF: a deeper analysis of these, and their connections to each other and to the omics stakeholders, will be provided in the deliverable from T3.3.

Notably, OBIS and GBIF harvest data from the same source points, which are national or thematic nodes, allowing for “publish data once, harvest often”. Afterwards, they do not directly exchange data. This requires data providers submitting their data through an IPT (Integrated Publishing Toolkit) instance to specifically indicate whether their data needs to flow to OBIS, GBIF or both.

The (meta)data to be published with eDNA-based occurrences should include the taxonomic classification, information on the origin of the classification, some measure of the quantity of the organism, a place and a date of the occurrence, and sufficient information to allow the provenance of the derivation of the occurrence to be provided (the who, what, where, when, and how).

Figure 7: Biodiversity occurrence eDNA related (meta)data is currently deposited in a plethora of generalist and specialist repositories. This can be in many different formats or no-structure. N.B. This is a sub graph of the above

What works well

- GBIF and OBIS both use DwC(-A), and communicate on their use of the DNA extension.
- They both also harvest metadata and data from other regional and thematic data publishers in Europe and beyond, resulting in a more interoperable and global sharing of data.
- GBIF and OBIS (including EurOBIS) also use EML as the dataset discovery and description metadata schema, and are exposing metadata also as JSON-LD.
- The DNA sequences that correspond to the occurrences can be submitted to the DwC-A DNA extension, providing a place for these data to be archived.
 - Currently, it is not possible to search in GBIF or OBIS specifically on these parts of the data, but that is expected to change in the future. E.g. for now, OBIS has a filter to find data with sequences attached. In the future, filters will be added to search for target genes and primer sets. OBIS is also planning to implement a search based on sequence similarity (blast/vsearch like).
- There are many repositories, in particular on the national scale, in which biodiversity data can be published, and more and more are accepting DNA-based results.
- Well-written guidelines on [Publishing DNA-derived data through biodiversity data platforms](#) exist and are regularly updated (Abarenkov et al. 2023, last updated 27 February 2025)

What does not work well

- There is currently only limited mapping of MixS-based resources such as INSDC to DwC. Currently only the DwC core terms are mapped to MixS, not the DwC extensions. In addition, there are differences in the descriptions and examples of how to use some of the terms, leading to potential divergence between MixS and DwC.
- To ensure high-quality data, all information in the submitted (meta)data should be interoperable (terms provided as URIs rather than strings, protocols made to be accessible, etc) which is currently not fully enforced, and more metadata fields than is currently the case should be made mandatory. This will be discussed in the final deliverable of T3.3.
- While there is no lack of repositories to publish biodiversity data, there is still a lot that is only published in scientific journals (either within the papers or in the generalist repositories connected to those journals).
- When publishing marine data to either OBIS or GBIF, publishing nodes or individuals need to explicitly decide to publish to both databases. This means that not all marine data published to

GBIF automatically appears on OBIS, and *vice versa*, and the research community needs to be educated on the importance of choosing the right destination for their dataset, explicitly requesting both where applicable.

- A significant barrier to the update of submitting eDNA-based occurrences is the lack of tools and templates to easily translate bioinformatics outputs into data accepted by the repositories. This is in particular the case with submitted data as DwC-A.
 - The [GBIF Metabarcoding Data Toolkit](#) is significantly important here for single and/or small datasets.
 - Several bioinformatic pipelines (see above) include a DwC conversion step. More consolidated approaches in this direction would be helpful.
 - It is important to stress that it is *not* necessary that bioinformatics outputs are converted to DwC-A (there is no need to fix yourself to a particular standard and its particular schema), but rather that they are (*machine-*)*interoperable* so that converting those outputs to DwC-A, or any other standard and schema, is easy.

Taxonomic backbones used in eDNA-based biodiversity (meta)data

There are many taxonomic backbones – systems that provide curated taxonomic names and their hierarchy in a database to which each name has a unique and permanent ID: WoRMS and the NCBI taxonomy are two important stakeholders here. There are two main origins of taxonomies in the ecosystem, a) traditional ones (e.g. WoRMS) which historically has been from material evidence of actual individual specimens, requiring much expert curation and b) the omics based (e.g. NCBI), are linked to DNA-evidence, are high throughput and are often less curated. The omics based taxonomies have unknown or unconfirmed species.

Some taxonomies have widespread coverage of all organisms (e.g. NCBI), others focus on marine organisms with scientific depth (e.g. WoRMS) or particular kingdoms or taxonomic classes (e.g. Index Fungorum). Biodiversity databases, especially those that use the DwC/DwC-A standard, use these names and often also identifiers in the taxonomic backbone as part of the taxonomic information they require. Reliable taxonomic information is necessary to place the occurrences in the wider context of biodiversity, biology, ecology, etc., and providing the IDs is necessary to make that information accessible in the long-term, reusable, and unambiguous.

From the WP2 questionnaire survey to institutes producing reference sequences, WoRMS was the primary taxonomic source used, with approximately 24% of the cases. GBIF and NCBI taxonomy were also notable.

The biodiversity data, in particular that provided in the DwC-A standard, should include the taxonomic information about each occurrence reported on. The information in the metadata, however, should be sufficiently rich to enable others to infer what taxonomic groups may be found in the data (e.g. source of the sample, size fraction if relevant, primer specificity (for metabarcoding data), reference databases used, etc.). If a specific taxonomic group was targeted, the metadata should state this in order to allow the dataset to be found in the data repository via taxonomic search keys.

Some taxonomic backbones also include potentially novel and undescribed or unnamed taxa, that are derived from curation of DNA sequences, as for example BOLD (the BOLD BINs) or UNITE (Species Hypotheses), that also hold persistent identifiers. Some biodiversity databases, such as GBIF, allow to directly add BIN-IDs in the ID field. For OBIS, such classification is added as unknown and BIN-IDs etc are included in other fields (like taxonConceptID). It's important to note that not all occurrences need to have a known taxonomy, you can still record the sequence in OBIS/GBIF.

Figure 8. Taxonomic backbones and the associated taxonomic identifier are used to unambiguously annotate the taxonomic identity of the organismal source of eDNA. Note the mix of specialist (e.g. Algaebase) and generalist (e.g. NCBI) taxonomies.

What works well

- As OBIS and GBIF require at least a scientific name, and an ID, these information tend to be well provided in submitted eDNA-based datasets. If no scientific name ID can be found (this is also searched for automatically if not provided), then the records are flagged and dropped. However, the scientific name can be a very high level taxonomic group such as a phylum or a class.
- A scientific name is also required for nucleotide sequence submission to INSDC (including also the NCBI taxonomy identifier) and BOLD.
- While there are many backbones used, there is also much work done by these systems to map to each other such as between WoRMS and NCBI. The Catalogue of Life (COL) and GBIF both contribute to ChecklistBank (<https://www.checklistbank.org/>) which is a standardised repository of taxonomic datasets.

What does not work well

- Genomics taxonomic systems, especially if arising from custom reference libraries (i.e. those produced as part of a single person's work for a particular purpose), do not always provide and sustain the provision of permanent and unique IDs for the names. This breaks machine interoperability and limits the long-term usefulness of the data.
- Taxonomic annotations used in genetic reference databases are variable and there is no agreed upon central standard.
 - As more genetic information becomes available, higher level taxonomic names increasingly follow a cladistic system as opposed to the traditional systems like the one of Linné. At higher taxonomic levels, least common ancestors are increasingly difficult to identify meaning that taxonomic changes at these levels (class, phylum or even kingdom) are expected to continue for the foreseeable future.
 - The increasing adoption of cladistic systematics has led to an increased use of intermediate taxonomic levels in order to communicate about well-known taxonomic groups. For example, flatfishes are not grouped anymore in their own order (former Pleuronectiformes) but as a sub-order (Pleuronectoidei) of jacks (Carangiformes).
 - As another example, PR2 recently changed the way they annotate their sequences from eight to nine taxonomic levels (<https://pr2-database.org/post/news/2023-04-06-pr2-version-5.0/>)
 - The number of taxonomic levels may differ by field. While in botany, cultivars have their own taxonomic rank at the infraspecific level, the subspecies concept has been almost abandoned for fishes. In other vertebrate groups, however, subspecific epithets are still widely used (e.g. for reptiles).

- The need for taxonomic levels may vary depending on the diversity in a specific group. For example, the family of Cichlidae has more than 2000 species and subfamily and tribe names are frequently used in the scientific literature to facilitate communication. In contrast, the sister taxon of Cichlidae, the Pholidichthyidae, includes only two extant species that belong to the same genus rendering subfamily and tribe names obsolete.
- All the reference databases use a different format (or fasta header), which makes it complicated to make general purpose pipelines, let alone be sure they are comparable with each other
- However, a lot refer back to NCBI-IDs.
- Conciliation of data on classical (morphotaxonomic) taxonomic assignments and DNA-based taxonomic assignments. When organisms have been morphologically identified as belonging to a group that is now considered polyphyletic, the scientific name should be changed to a higher level taxon. For example, a specimen that has been identified as *Hyphessobrycon* sp. may now be classified as Acestorhamphidae at the family level as species formerly assigned to *Hyphessobrycon* are now split over several different genera in several different subfamilies. This may lead to a perceived loss of taxonomic resolution in the data. However, it rather reflects our incomplete knowledge on biodiversity in the past.

Biobanks Data - Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility

Biobanks are curated collections of biological samples stored and preserved at different levels from individual to molecular level, typically frozen, along with associated data, and managed according to scientific standards. They serve as critical infrastructures for biodiversity conservation, research, and applications in fields such as genomics, ecology, and biotechnology. Biodiversity and environmental biobanks encompass a wide range of samples, including tissues, DNA, living cells, seeds, dead and alive specimens, and even environmental samples from matrices like soil and water. These collections are housed in diverse settings such as culture collections, natural history museums, botanical gardens, zoos, and universities.

The Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) (https://www.ggbn.org/ggbn_portal/) is an international network of institutions that share an interest in long-term preservation of genomic samples representing the diversity of non-human life on Earth. The GGBN provides its members with the primary benefit of making their DNA and tissue collections discoverable for research through a networked community of biodiversity biobanks. Over thirty of the GGBN biobanks were sent a questionnaire asking questions about their metadata and standards, to find out the current state of play.

One of the most striking features of biobanks is their heterogeneity. This variability manifests in several dimensions:

- Scope and Focus: Biobanks may specialise in specific taxa (e.g., plants, animals, microorganisms) or types of samples (e.g., DNA, germplasm, environmental samples, specimens).
- Operational Practices: Procedures for collection, preservation, storage, and data management vary widely, often lacking international standardisation. However, there are ongoing activities that aim to change this within the next 5 years.
- Infrastructure: Facilities range from room-temperature storage for dried specimens to cryogenic conditions for viable tissues, among others
- Governance and Policies: Adherence to international regulations and guidelines (e.g., Nagoya Protocol, ISBER guidelines) is inconsistent, and policies on sample access and benefit-sharing differ significantly.

This heterogeneity poses both opportunities and challenges. While it allows biobanks to cater to specific research or conservation needs, it also complicates efforts to harmonise practices, share resources, and ensure data comparability across institutions.

Aquatic environment biobanks represent a specialised and increasingly important subset of biodiversity repositories. These collections focus on preserving biological materials from marine, freshwater, and brackish water ecosystems, which cover over 70% of Earth's surface and harbour immense biodiversity. Aquatic biobanks face unique challenges and opportunities:

Sample Types and Preservation Methods

Aquatic biobanks maintain diverse collections including, marine and freshwater organism tissues cells, or individuals of animals, plants, and microorganisms, and environmental DNA (eDNA) from water samples. Plankton collections (phytoplankton and zooplankton), sediment cores containing microbial communities and ancient DNA, cryopreserved gametes and embryos of endangered aquatic species, coral fragments and symbiotic associations, or microalgal culture collections are just examples of these biobanks. Preservation techniques for aquatic samples often require specialised approaches due to high water content, salt concentration, and the fragility of many specimens.

Research Applications

Aquatic biobanks support diverse scientific endeavors like monitoring of ecosystem health and biodiversity changes, assessment of climate change impacts on aquatic environments, detection and tracking of invasive species, bioprospecting for novel compounds from aquatic organisms, conservation of endangered aquatic species through genetic resource banking, studies of evolutionary adaptations to aquatic environments or microbiome research in water systems, among others.

Unique Challenges

Aquatic biobanks face distinct challenges:

- Collection logistics: Sampling in remote ocean environments or at extreme depths requires specialised equipment and vessels.
- Preservation challenges: Many marine organisms contain high salt concentrations or compounds that can interfere with DNA extraction and preservation.
- Legal complexities: International waters and disputed maritime boundaries create jurisdictional issues for sample collection and associated rights.
- Rapidly changing environments: Climate change, ocean acidification, and pollution are transforming aquatic ecosystems at unprecedented rates, creating urgency for comprehensive sampling.
- Cryptic diversity: Many aquatic organisms, especially microorganisms and deep-sea species, remain undescribed, complicating taxonomic classification of samples.

Global Initiatives and Networks

Several international efforts are working to coordinate aquatic biobanking activities, more specifically The Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) includes numerous marine and freshwater biobank collections. The Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) coordinates marine biodiversity data, including also those associated with biobank specimens, The Genomic Observatories Network focuses on genomic sampling across marine and freshwater ecosystems, and the Marine Barcode of Life (MarBOL) initiative aims to DNA barcode all marine species. These collective efforts are working

to address the fragmentation in aquatic biobanking through harmonised protocols, metadata requirements, and ethical frameworks for sample use.

The compiled literature and survey of Europe's aquatic biobanks reveal both strengths and weaknesses in current biobanking approaches. Biobanks demonstrate significant strengths in diverse sample preservation, specimen-genetic data integration, taxonomic reference system usage, and digital accessibility, with many institutions adopting advanced technologies and joining collaborative networks to enhance sample management and respond to growing research demands. However, they face substantial challenges including inconsistent data standards, limited information sharing, inadequate sample traceability, variable DNA management practices, poor bioinformatics integration, taxonomic reference inconsistencies, underrepresentation of certain species, and insufficient backup systems. This contrast between successful preservation practices and standardization difficulties highlights the need for greater harmonisation across biobanking institutions to maximise their scientific and conservation potential.

Figure 9. Biobanks and culture collections that generate sequence data typically deposit this in either nucleotide databases (mostly INSDC databases), or keep them in-house which hinders reuse. Biobanks benefit from taxonomic expertise to identify their specimens (typically using trustworthy taxonomic identification based on e.g. good taxonomic expertise and classification keys) on the basis of morphological (for macroorganisms) or the physiological/metabolic (for prokaryotes) traits, and to curate the sequence data they generate.

What works well

- **Diverse Sample Collection and Preservation.** Biobanks successfully preserve a broad spectrum of biological materials, including tissues, DNA, living cells, seeds, individuals (including voucher specimens), and environmental samples. A voucher specimen is a preserved sample of a plant or animal that serves as a verifiable record of a species. This diversity supports a wide range of research and conservation applications, from genomics to species restoration. European biobanks are successfully preserving diverse DNA-related materials using advanced techniques such as liquid nitrogen gas phase storage for long-term viability. All surveyed biobanks include DNA-related materials or data, demonstrating the central importance of genetic resources in modern biological collections.
- **Integration of Genetic Data with Specimens.** Biobanks consistently establish connections between physical specimens and their derived genetic information through structured metadata systems. All surveyed institutions maintain DNA-related fields in their metadata and

provide links to datasets and publications through persistent identifiers or DOIs, creating traceable pathways from specimens to research outputs.

- **Taxonomic Reference Systems.** Biobanks utilise established taxonomic reference systems like the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) and Catalogue of Life (CoL), ensuring scientific accuracy in specimen identification. Some institutions further enhance taxonomic information by referencing molecular databases like NCBI and ENA, recognising the importance of genetic data in modern taxonomy.
- **Digital Accessibility.** Two-thirds of surveyed biobanks already provide online access to their collections, with the remaining institutions actively working toward digital transformation. This improves visibility and facilitates research access to valuable genetic resources.
- **Integration of Technology.** Biobanks are increasingly digitizing their collections and using online databases to enhance accessibility. Tools like the Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) and barcoding improve sample tracking and data management. Most biobanks maintain connections to DNA extraction and analysis capabilities, either through in-house laboratories with automated extraction technology or partnerships with external facilities.
- **Networking and Collaboration.** Institutions are joining global networks like the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) to share knowledge, harmonise practices, and improve sample discoverability. Other initiatives, such as the World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC) for the case of microorganism, a multidisciplinary commission of the International Union of Biological Sciences (IUBS) and a Federation within the International Union of Microbiological Societies (IUMS), are specialised in particular types of organisms. Collaborative efforts also facilitate capacity-building, particularly in developing countries.
- **Focus on Quality Control.** Many biobanks perform regular quality checks on samples, such as DNA integrity tests and viability assessments for living materials. This ensures the long-term usability of stored specimens.
- **Response to Increasing Demand.** Half of the surveyed institutions reported a rise in sample requests, driven by digitization and growing research collaborations. Biobanks are adapting by improving their workflows and expanding services.

What does not work well

- **Inconsistent Data Standards and Formats.** Despite the importance of standardization, biobanks use diverse approaches for metadata management, ranging from sophisticated databases compliant with database standards to basic Word or Excel documents. This inconsistency creates challenges for data integration and comparison across institutions. Practices for sample collection, preservation, and storage vary widely, even within the same institution. Biobanks adhering to defined best practices are a minority. Many institutions still rely on Excel sheets or internal databases, limiting interoperability. Only a very small fraction of biobanks link their databases to LIMS.
- **Limited Information Sharing.** Several biobanks maintain more comprehensive internal data than what is made available online. For instance, some institutions noted that not all data fields in their databases are shown publicly, suggesting missed opportunities for knowledge sharing and collaboration.
- **Inadequate Sample Traceability.** Collection permits and metadata are often stored separately from samples, complicating compliance with regulations like the Nagoya Protocol. Only a low percentage of biobanks systematically track research outputs derived from their samples, missing opportunities to demonstrate their impact.
- **Variable Growth in DNA Service Demand.** While there is a general trend toward increased requests for genetic materials, the growth is inconsistent across institutions. Some report specific increases in requests for DNA barcode marker sequences, while others note only modest increases in genomic DNA requests, indicating uneven development across the field.

- **Emerging DNA Management Practices.** Some institutions characterised their DNA-related services as nascent or "only starting," suggesting varying levels of maturity in genetic resource management across biobanks. This creates challenges for researchers seeking consistent access to DNA resources.
- **Limited DNA-Specific Metadata Standards.** While biobanks implement various biodiversity standards, there appears to be a lack of DNA-specific, internationally accepted metadata standards universally applied across institutions. This hampers interoperability for genetic information specifically.
- **Variable DNA Storage Methodologies.** Biobanks employ different approaches to DNA storage, from sophisticated cryopreservation to more basic preservation methods. These variations can affect DNA quality and usability for different research applications.
- **Incomplete Integration with Bioinformatics Resources.** Few biobanks provided detailed information about advanced genomic and bioinformatic data management, suggesting potential gaps in connecting physical specimens and genetic data with computational resources needed for modern genetic analysis.
- **Taxonomic Information Challenges.** The varied taxonomic reference systems used by different biobanks can create challenges when comparing or integrating DNA data across institutions, particularly for less-studied organisms or those with complex taxonomic histories.
- **Underrepresentation of Certain Taxa.** Samples from threatened or rare species are frequently insufficient, and strategies to replenish or amplify DNA are not consistently applied. In general, for macroorganisms, only a small part of the described species is deposited in biobanks or culture collections. Further, for specific ecosystem types, microbial diversity is often underrepresented due to culturing difficulties.
- **Limited Backup and Redundancy.** Few biobanks maintain duplicate collections in geographically separate locations, risking irreversible loss in case of equipment failure or disasters.

Future landscape recommendations

Based on the representation of the current landscape, and assessment of its strengths and weaknesses, the eDNAqua-Plan consortium identified areas, notes, bottlenecks that need improvement and proposed solutions to achieve this. These recommendations are being iterated over as the project advances, and should not be taken as final in the current document [v1.0].

Overall landscape

The current digital aquatic eDNA data landscape overall has the needed infrastructure. However, though the resources exist, there is work needed regarding data/metadata linking and enhancing accessibility and interoperability between infrastructures, and also improving usage/data submission to the right resources following community guidelines and internationally accepted standards.

For researchers to use the landscape, and improve data availability, guidance is needed in how and where to submit their data. Ideally, internationally agreed methodological standards that outline procedural minimum requirements also include requirements for reporting, which would ensure relevant (meta)data are collected and reported as the methodological standards are being applied. International sampling and laboratory method standardisation is already under way and will become an important stepping stone which will simplify the current situation. In the meantime however it is important that each research group creates a clear data management plan (DMP) before embarking on their project, outlining specifically what (meta)data will be collected at each stage and which repositories to submit them to. Obviously adherence to FAIR (Wilkinson et al. 2016), CARE (Carrol et al 2020) and in some cases TRUST (Lin et al. 2020) principles underpin the DMP. Too often depositing even the minimum (meta)data is an afterthought, done in hurry in order to be referenced in a scientific publication. In the future, adherence to international methodological standards will create appropriate (meta)data in a more seamless manner. In the short term however, a HowTo guidance flowchart would be useful and aid constructing an appropriate DMP. Another exciting long term prospect is the creation of a “one stop shop” tool to input all your data into, that will flow to all relevant repositories. While we are aware that the creation of such a tool is non-trivial, it is a worthwhile effort that would hugely impact the data producing community.

Some tools and guidance already exist for managing eDNA data:

- The NOAA Omics Data Management Guide:
<https://noaa-omics-dmg.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- The FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) Guidelines: <https://fair-edna.github.io/guidelines.html>

The eDNAqua-Plan project can then provide DMP templates for different data types:

- Quantification (qPCR/ddPCR)
- Metabarcoding
- Metagenomics

AI has many potential uses in biodiversity, e.g. digital twins (Reynolds et al. 2025). Providing readily accessible, comprehensive and interoperable meta(data) has increasing prominence as this reduces the friction of using the dataset for both non-AI and AI computational usages. An appropriate DMP facilitates this.

Figure 10: To improve the future eDNA digital landscape, there needs to be proactive management of what (meta)data is needed and where it should be stored.

Dichotomy of approaches

The future landscape, as we recommend it, would have different approaches for reference libraries, nucleotide and biodiversity databases. For reference databases, we suggest that they become connected to each other as a decentralised network of servers capable of communicating directly with each other and exchanging data. This decentralised structure is needed to sustainably maintain the wide diversity of existing reference databases, often focusing on specific genetic markers or taxonomic groups.

For raw (and in the future potentially processed) eDNA data, a few central and broad-scope repositories already exist and are in common use for data submission and access. They successfully exchange data daily through the INSDC collaboration.

For biodiversity data, including processed eDNA data as occurrence ASV/OTU and taxonomic identifications, many nation-, region- or organisation-specific repositories exist. These do not exist as a network communicating with each-other directly, but often make (a subset of) their data available through a few broad-scope repositories, e.g. GBIF and OBIS. These broad-scope repositories are already in place and provide a sustainable federated platform for data sharing. These work well in providing a centralised access to decentralised repositories, only if these specific repositories appropriately share their data and metadata.

Modern Good Practice for Data

Ensuring FAIRness is essential. Our future data ecosystem data entities need to be annotated with ideally a persistent URL (PURL) or at least a persistent identifier (PID) to ensure machine interoperability and even findability.

Linked open data (LOD) and exposing metadata and data via W3C standard protocols makes all (meta)data accessible to everyone, equally, in a machine-understandable standard way and this avoids many of the interoperability and accessibility issues in the ecosystem. The Resource Description Framework (RDF) is machine interoperable and semantically annotated so fully understandable by automated processes.

Community Buy-In and Wider Community Responsibilities

We acknowledge that it is the responsibility of all of the stakeholders, for the PI's planning the project, to researchers sampling, laboratory staff, bioinformaticians, repository maintainers, publishers, funders etc. to improve the data ecosystem.

Improving the data ecosystem will require much more than just having standards and appropriate repositories. The environment needs to encourage, champion and reward efforts to deposit data and meet FAIR principles. One hurdle data generators face is feeling that they cannot get the right credit for publishing their datasets, thus not having the right incentive to do so. Many/most database publishers produce DOIs of datasets. A solution to this is offered by the possibility of claiming ownership of ENA data by an ORCID (<https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq/orcid-claiming.html>). GBIF and OBIS also assign DOIs to all datasets and track citations.

Sampling

- There is a clear need for stricter and better provision of provenance metadata. Sufficient sampling metadata should always be collected and reported in a standardised manner. While currently only few such standards exist, the expert community is working to establish them for future use (e.g. ISO-EN 17805 Sampling, capture and preservation of environmental DNA from water).
- Pathways to deposit sample metadata in the appropriate data repositories (e.g. biosamples) and linked in the biodiversity occurrence databases should be made mandatory.
- More mandatory metadata fields need to be established focussing on what is needed for FAIR.
- More enforcement of the content of the metadata to be interoperable is needed
 - Harmonisation and mapping of vocabularies
 - Guidance for finding the correct term in standardised checklists e.g. for geographical locations (GAZ), habitats (ENVO); ISO standardised terminology (Online browsing platform, ODB or laboratory machinery (OBI).
- Increased use of RDF, LOD, and web-tech to expose the dataset metadata and make the datasets findable and accessible.
- Smartphone apps can be useful in biodiversity monitoring to streamline the collection of sample information, furthermore they can be used to increase the accuracy and conformity to protocols. Examples include:
 - The NMDC Field Notes mobile app (<https://microbiomedata.org/field-notes/>). This has automated synchronicity with environment-specific templates (e.g., soil or water).
 - The PlutoF GO app (<https://plutof.ut.ee/go>). Information is transferred to the PlutoF workbench and allows further detail to be added there.

Laboratory Procedures

- Sufficient laboratory processing metadata should always be collected and reported in a standardised manner. Ideally the collection of such metadata is a byproduct of the application of laboratory method standards.
- The Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) should be fully utilised to generate required metadata in a standardised way.
- Standardised protocols should be applied or individual protocols need to be deposited into an appropriate, open resource repository and referenced with the metadata accompanying the raw sequence data.

Raw Sequence Data

- Always deposit the raw sequence data into an open access nucleotide sequence repository, ideally an INSDC (NCBI, ENA or DDBJ) repository.
 - Always publish data - recommendation is an open access licence with data downloadable immediately via that repo/portal (rather than “on demand” from the data provider)
 - Always use specialised repositories before using generalist ones.
- More mandatory metadata fields, focus on what is needed for FAIR.
- More enforcement of the content of the metadata to be interoperable.
- More use of RDF, LOD, and web-tech to expose the dataset metadata and make the datasets findable and accessible.
- Stricter and better provision of provenance metadata.

Bioinformatics Analysis

- Always capture the bioinformatics workflows, and the underlying program versions and options in a suitable repository to ensure reproducibility and reusability.
- Define and keep intermediary files, with naming conventions.
- Include or link this bioinformatics metadata into the processed eDNA data in a standardised format
 - The FAIR checklist project led by Miwa Takahashi (Making eDNA FAIR) captured much metadata including nomenclature of intermediate files, and defined different requirement levels of each metadata field.
 - These include a few essential fields that will allow the interpretation and reuse of the data. E.g. clustering or error-filtering parameters, taxonomic identification confidence levels.
- More use of RDF, LOD, and web-technology to expose the dataset metadata and make the datasets findable and accessible.

Processed Sequence Data

- Better data integration from national and institutional databases into global databases.
- Ensure linkage between upcoming ASV/OTU services (ENA, GBIF & OBIS, BOLD).
- A change in data publishing practices, from none or non-FAIR repositories into FAIR ones. Proposed solutions:
 - work with publishers/journals to ensure sequence data has an accession id
 - Work towards better dataset citation and crediting.
- More use of RDF, LOD, and web-tech to expose the dataset metadata and make the datasets findable and accessible.
- When re-processing eDNA data, changes in taxonomic assignment need to be dealt with efficiently to avoid inflating biodiversity records by assigning the same record twice or more to different organisms.

Taxonomic assignment

A network of connected, searchable and reliable reference libraries

- Success means: all taxonomic assignments of eDNA data are done using quality-controlled, taxonomically curated and thus reliable reference databases.
- These are easy to find and connected to each other (mapped to each other as well).
- It's easy for users to know whether any reference sequence follows a curation and quality standard.
- Not one large taxonomically-curated eDNA reference database of aquatic organisms of Europe (not feasible, necessary or desirable) but a diverse portfolio of independent databases. Each of the current curated databases are created and maintained by different groups or institutions and each of these databases have their own focus, specialisation, taxonomic specialists and management. This diversity in existing databases should be maintained.
- A network of open linked data resources, QC & curated reference libraries.
- A federated (meta)data search engine to find the right (eDNAqua-Plan approved) library and sequence.
- More use of RDF, LOD, and web-tech to expose the taxonomic names (and associated information) and their assigned PIDs.

The ideal future landscape would consist of independently curated and maintained databases/libraries which follow common, guiding principles, are interconnected, and searchable through a common metadata portal. The reference databases/libraries undergo a curation of metadata, taxonomic name

validation but also taxonomic accuracy to ensure reliable taxonomic assignment. These follow a set of essential metadata requirements and curation principles proposed by the eDNAqua-Plan consortium and approved by the relevant wider community. If a reference database follows these metadata and curation requirements, they receive the community-approved quality label which allows users to know the quality, metadata and curation requirements are met. All “approved” reference databases are interconnected using the same communication protocols and searchable through the common metadata search tool/engine. However, they maintain their independence though (e.g. through independent servers). Finally, this curation would create feedback that goes back to the data providers, especially correcting taxonomic assignment errors.

Figure 11. In the future, all reference databases would follow a set of common quality-control, metadata and taxonomic curation principles to ensure the reliability of the reference sequences. These reference databases would then be integrated in a network of open linked data resources. They would be findable and searchable through a common metadata search portal, allowing users to be pointed to the right, reliable resource.

To achieve this future landscape, our recommendations would follow these steps:

1. Define and recommend essential metadata which enable a quality-control and curation (and thus establish the reliability of the taxonomic assignment later on):
 - a. These include recommendations on tracking sequence and assignment provenance to avoid artificially inflating biodiversity. By always linking taxonomic assignment to the original sequence in research data portals, we avoid problems caused by different taxonomic assignments of the same source data which are then uploaded to data research databases.
 - b. RO-Crate (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>) could be a solution, as it allows complex data to be captured in a structured form(JSON).
 - c. Anchor essential metadata in international methodological and laboratory standards to ensure wide adherence and their uptake.
2. Define and recommend common taxonomic curation principles:
 - a. Another expected key outcome from our work would be to contribute to the taxonomic community (experts who identify, name, describe, and classify biodiversity working from the level of molecules, including eDNA and eRNA, genomes and metagenomes, species and populations, to habitats and ecosystems), and ensure that its capacity to engage with and support policy and other decision-making are strengthened.

- b. Again, iBOL-Europe was cited here alongside the upcoming call HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-03: Strengthening taxonomic approaches for biodiversity.
 - c. Anchor minimum taxonomic curation principles in international standards.
3. Create a recognition system of databases/libraries that follow these recommendations
 - a. This could help databases get funding to be sustainable. The lack of long term funding for the curation of reference databases is a problem. We could envision a certification or quality label at the EU-level where the curation of reference databases is recognised as strategically important, and databases get recognised as following the EU-level scientific curation requirements. Such certification or label could help in getting national funding.
 - b. The Global Biodata Coalition (<https://globalbiodata.org>) was cited as an organisation that assesses biological databases globally.
4. Establish connections between recognised/curated databases so they can communicate through an integrated network.
 - a. Here, metadata recommendations should focus on interoperability through common metadata standard vocabulary (e.g. MIxS vocabulary).
 - b. To step up the findability, accessibility from the above, additionally the recommendation is to output data in JSON-LD or potentially an equivalent. This makes it much easier for machines as well as humans to find and digest metadata.
 - c. This can be a protocol of data and metadata exchange between reference libraries. Any reference library following this exchange will be part of the network (irrespective of the country of origin). There are some existing data exchange protocols that we can borrow ideas from, e.g. HUPO-PSI.
5. Create a metadata search portal/engine to query the “accredited” reference databases that follow the eDNAqua-Plan recommendation or compliant international standards. This approach would maintain the diversity in existing databases, while ensuring common curation requirements are met for reliability.
 - a. Inspiration could be taken from the Genomes on a Tree metadata portal from the Earth Biogenome Project <https://goat.genomehubs.org>).
 - b. iBOL Europe or the European eDNA Society, which are both gaining momentum, could be a potential central hubs for this.
6. Establish a feedback system from curators and users back to the data providers in primary platforms.
 - a. Currently, records in the primary databases are meant to be an archival copy. The ELIXIR Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH) however allows the addition of annotations to ENA objects, which are shown alongside the archived records. A feedback loop is already in place between UNITE and ENA using the CDCH.

eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases

The ideal future landscape would have the following points:

- All eDNA-based occurrences to be published as biodiversity data, and not only in publications or not published at all. This applies even where no scientific paper is produced from a project.
- All eDNA-based occurrences to be published in biodiversity repositories which are searchable and interoperable, rather than generalised ones.
- Have the various national to global and thematic biodiversity data publishers to be working together to adopt common data and metadata standards and schema.
- Additionally, more communication between the largest levers in the biodiversity data world (in particular GBIF and OBIS) with the largest levers in the eDNA world (including GSC and INSDC), to align standards (in particular in the use of vocabularies).

- More mandatory information needs to be required from published data, and interoperable data contents promoted. For example URIs or even better PURLs rather than strings, allow machines to reliably use values.
 - Ideally, these should be enforced by the databases themselves (e.g. ENA, NCBI, GBIF, OBIS).
 - If this is not feasible, eDNAqua-Plan could propose a certification process to recognise entries with sufficient and quality-controlled data.
 - This would be based on a set of essential metadata terms agreed upon by the wider community, and operational (meta)data standards.
 - The databases would then need to implement this quality label recognition.
- Biodiversity databases should implement key QC checks to validate the eDNA data in their databases and ensure the correct reuse by non-eDNA experts.
- To publish more metadata as RDF, using LOD and web standards to exposure the dataset discovery and description metadata to everyone.
- Publishing also more of the data using LOD and web standards to expose the data to everyone.
- To adopt more provenance templates when describing data originating from biological (and in our case, eDNA) material. Such templates should be created, e.g. via community collaborating
- To have better mapping of omics and traditional taxonomic naming systems so that eDNA results are more discoverable and understandable by biodiversity data users.
- To increase interoperable and open data originating from bioinformatics pipelines, which then can allow more generalised tools to be created to convert those to whatever format and schema the biodiversity data publishers require (which at present is DwC-A and the DwC vocabulary).
 - GBIF is releasing the [Darwin Core Data Package \(DwC-DP\)](#) Publishing Model that implements the conceptual model and supports sharing deeper and richer data than is possible with a Darwin Core Archive. At the time of writing, this is still emerging with a public review beginning 2025-09-01.

Figure 12. In the future, eDNA-based biodiversity data will be deposited in the appropriate databases at their respective organisational level, to then be integrated by global data aggregators which will include tailored quality-control and validation criteria.

Taxonomic backbone

- Differences and changes in different taxonomic references need to be dealt with efficiently and of course scientifically correctly.

Biobanks Data - Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility

As climate change and habitat destruction accelerate biodiversity loss in aquatic ecosystems, biobanks will play an increasingly vital role in preserving genetic resources that might otherwise be lost forever. Integration of cutting-edge technologies like single-cell genomics, long-read sequencing, and artificial intelligence for taxonomy will enhance the scientific value of these collections. Additionally, increased engagement with local communities and local people in coastal and riverside areas will improve ethical practices and benefit-sharing arrangements for aquatic biobank collections. Harmonization or standardisation of procedures, including not only sample collection and laboratory procedures, but also metadata generation and interoperability with biodiversity repositories, are nowadays the main challenge to be afforded for the integration of biobanks information following FAIR principles.

- The remaining institutions need to continue to be actively working toward digital accessibility.
- Most institutions need to improve workflow tracking (e.g. Laboratory Information Management Systems LIMS) and generally to move towards databases (away from Excel), to continue the digital transformation.
- Some institutions could also increase the amount of data that they share.
 - E.g. Most institutions need to provide detailed metadata about advanced genomic and bioinformatic workflows. (see the handling of workflows elsewhere.)
- To use more standards, to allow increased interoperability and thus *de facto* harmonisation:
 - DNA-specific metadata standards
 - Taxonomic
- A suggestion is to have a quality label where an institutional BioBank is complying with appropriate good practice and standards.

Figure 13. a) Each Biobank and collection sample to have improved standardise metadata b) be sequenced, taxonomic identity ascertained and linked to a BioSample identifier in an INSDC db, along with the sequence and BioProject(study metadata).

Conclusion

To improve the future eDNA digital landscape, there needs to be proactive management of what (meta)data is needed and where it should be stored. The majority of repositories needed for a vastly improved aquatic eDNA data ecosystem already exist. There are many examples of good practice and existing standards and guidelines. An important step is that the expert community inclusively co-develops methodological standards for method use in legislative and regulatory contexts that will include the production of required metadata as a byproduct of the proper use of the standard.

However, to increase the research community's participation, acknowledgements and data attribution is fundamental: e.g. a) data citation for data deposited and b) some type of certification/quality label of repositories that adhere to appropriate standards.

There will be significant costs associated with the improvements of the repositories and also time costs associated with the researchers depositing more and better quality meta(data). This should be accounted for and recognised as it will be more than offset by the increased availability, interoperability and sustainability of valuable biodiversity data for decades and beyond.

A very recent perspective covers much of the same points and more (Altermatt et al. 2025), and such will help us along with the WP feedback, as we work on the WP3 final deliverables.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the valuable input from all the other eDNAqua-Plan Work Packages for their deliverables and discussions. Special thanks to the eDNAqua-Plan Scientific Advisory board, particularly Jenny Giles (CSIRO) and Pier Luigi Buttigeig (AWI), for input into our standards workshop and other activities. We thank Tobias Guldberg Frøslev (GBIF) and Maria Kahlert (SLU) for their valuable contributions in the landscape workshop. Laurent Chmiel (OBIS) for significant help and advice with the Miro board, and Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI) for his review. Finally, we thank the eDNAqua-Plan members participating in the standards and landscape workshops, who are cited as contributors, as well as Paulina Marcella Ramírez Quevedo and Nicolas Pade for their advice and support.

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A few Mediterranean fish, both conspicuous and rare, swimming through the seascape. Credit: E. Boulanger

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

